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Research Article

EXPANSION AND VALUATION OF PIROXICAM MOUTH DISSOLVING MEDICATIONS

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The study focuses on the formulation and development of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Tablets (MDTs) to improve patient compliance, particularly for those with swallowing difficulties, such as the elderly and mentally ill. Excipients and Piroxicam were procured, with their identities confirmed via UV-visible and FT-IR spectroscopy. Multiple formulations were developed and optimized for rapid disintegration and dissolution, with formulation F6 identified as optimal in early tests. Further optimization, using experimental designs, identified formulation F9 as superior due to its enhanced disintegration properties. Preformulation studies assessed key parameters, including tablet appearance, melting point, weight uniformity, hardness, friability, wetting time, and disintegration time. Dissolution tests, conducted using the USP paddle method, helped determine the dissolution profile of the MDTs. Compatibility studies confirmed the stability of the drug and excipients under various conditions. Physical characterization was carried out using UV-spectrophotometric methods and FT-IR spectroscopy, and stability studies were conducted over three months at different temperatures and humidity levels to assess the shelf-life of the tablets. This study demonstrates the successful formulation, characterization, and stability of Piroxicam MDTs, highlighting their potential to improve patient adherence and the overall effectiveness of Piroxicam therapy.

Keywords: Piroxicam, UV, DSC, FT-IR etc.**Corresponding author:****Chandrakant P. Suryawanshi,**Affiliations: DCS's ARA College of Pharmacy,
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INTRODUCTION:

Piroxicam is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) commonly used to alleviate inflammation and pain, particularly in conditions such as arthritis. As a member of the oxicam class of NSAIDs, it functions by inhibiting the production of prostaglandins—chemical compounds in the body that contribute to inflammation and the sensation of pain.

Figure 01: Structure and IUPAC name of Piroxicam: 4-Hydroxy-2-methyl-N-(2-pyridinyl)-2H-1, 2-benzothiazine-3-carboxamide 1, 1-dioxide.

Class & Mechanism: Piroxicam, an oxicam-class NSAID, works by inhibiting cyclooxygenase (COX), reducing prostaglandin production, thus alleviating inflammation, pain, and fever.

Indications: Used to treat osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis, acute gout, menstrual cramps, and general pain.

Administration: Orally taken once daily, available in tablets, capsules, or topical forms.

Side Effects: Common side effects include stomach pain, nausea, diarrhea, dizziness, and headaches. Rare but serious effects can include gastrointestinal bleeding, kidney damage, and cardiovascular events.

Precautions: Caution for individuals with gastrointestinal ulcers, kidney, or heart problems. Not recommended in the third trimester of pregnancy or while breastfeeding.

Interactions & Monitoring: Piroxicam interacts with blood thinners, other NSAIDs, and antihypertensive drugs. Monitoring of kidney and liver function is advised.

Mouth Dissolving Tablets (MDTs): MDTs are designed for rapid disintegration in the mouth without water, enhancing convenience for patients with swallowing difficulties, such as the elderly or pediatric patients. They offer quick onset of action,

bypassing first-pass metabolism. MDTs are suitable for conditions requiring rapid relief, such as migraines or allergies.

Advantages:

1. Quick action and patient convenience.
2. Ideal for those with swallowing issues.
3. Portable, no water needed.
4. Enhanced bioavailability and therapeutic effects.

Disadvantages:

1. Require dry storage.
2. Fragile and need special packaging for stability.

Experimental:

Chemical and reagent: Piroxicam IP was received as a gift sample from Aarti Drugs Ltd. (India), while Carmellose Sodium (Ac-Di-Sol) was obtained from National Chemicals, Mumbai. Xylitol, Mannitol, and magnesium stearate were provided by Pure Pharma Limited, Indore. The identity of the samples was confirmed through UV-visible wavelength scans and FT-IR spectroscopy. FT-IR spectra were recorded using KBr pellets, and the UV-visible spectra of Piroxicam were recorded on a Shimadzu 1900i series instrument, using methanol and water as solvents.

Preformulation Studies for Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Tablets:**Evaluation Parameters:**

1. Appearance: Small, flat, round/oval, with a smooth surface and uniform color.
2. Size and Shape: Small, circular/oval, designed for rapid oral disintegration.
3. Weight Variation: Weigh 20 tablets individually and calculate the average weight.
4. Thickness: Measured using Vernier calipers.
5. Hardness: Measured using a Monsanto hardness tester.
6. Friability: Tested with a Roche friabilator, with weight loss not exceeding 1%.
7. Drug Content: Analyzed using UV spectrophotometry at 332 nm.
8. Wetting Time: Determined using the tissue paper method.
9. Disintegration Time: Target rapid disintegration in the mouth.
10. Dissolution Test: Performed in an appropriate dissolution medium.
11. Solubility: Measured in various solvents for Piroxicam.

Formulation Development for Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Tablets:

Preparation Method:

1. Sieving: Ensure uniform particle size distribution.
2. Mixing: Achieve a homogeneous distribution of drug and excipients.

3. Compression: Tablets compressed using a Cadmach compression machine with 10/32 round biconvex punches.

Table 01: Super disintegrants Selection:

Sr. no.	Batch No	Piroxicam (mg)	Ac-Di-Sol (mg)	Mannitol (mg)	Mg. Stearate (mg)	Total weight (mg)
1.	A1	10	10	176	4	200
2.	A2	10	14	172	4	200
3.	A3	10	18	168	4	200
4.	A4	10	22	164	4	200
5.	A5	10	26	160	4	200
6.	A6	10	30	156	4	200

Optimization of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets:

Procedure for Subliming Agents:

1. Formulated with camphor, menthol, and Thymol at various concentrations.
2. Subjected to sublimation at 40°C for 1 hour.
3. Assessed for friability, disintegration time, and hardness.

Table 02: Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets (A10) Formulations:

Ingredients (mgs)	Formulation Code (in mg)									
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
Piroxicam	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Mannitol	154	144	134	154	144	134	154	144	134	186
Ac-Di- Sol	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	0
Xylitol	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0
Camphor	10	20	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Menthol	0	0	0	10	20	30	0	0	0	0
Thymol	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	20	30	0
Magnesium stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Total	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

Physical Characterization and Compatibility Study:

1. Physical Characterization: Tablets were evaluated for appearance, weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, drug content, wetting time, disintegration time, dissolution, and solubility.

2. Compatibility Study: The drug and excipients were mixed in equal proportions and stored under different conditions (40°C, 25°C/RH 60%, and 40°C/RH 75%) for one month. The mixtures were analyzed using UV-visible spectrophotometry and FT-IR.

Stability Studies: Stability Studies: Conducted for 6 months at different temperatures (40°C, 25°C/RH 60%, 40°C/RH 75%). Samples were analyzed weekly for Piroxicam content using UV-visible spectrophotometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Confirmation of Identity of Piroxicam other excipients:**

Piroxicam IP was obtained as a gift sample from Pure Pharma Limited, Indore. Sodium Starch Glycolate was sourced from National Chemicals, Mumbai. Microcrystalline Cellulose, Colloidal Silicon Dioxide, Mannitol, and Sodium Saccharine were also received as gift samples from Pure Pharma Limited, Indore. The samples' identities were confirmed via UV-visible wavelength scan and FT-IR spectra. FT-IR spectra were recorded, and the UV-visible spectra of Piroxicam were recorded using methanol and water as solvents on a Shimadzu instrument.

Figure 02: Piroxicam λ -max maximum absorbance at 354 nm.

Figure no.03: FT-IR Interpretation of pure Piroxicam.

The UV-visible spectra of Piroxicam were recorded using methanol and water as solvents on a Shimadzu UV-1900i series instrument. Piroxicam typically exhibits maximum absorbance at approximately 332 nm, a wavelength commonly used for its quantitative analysis in pharmaceutical formulations.

FT-IR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) is employed to analyze the functional groups present in Piroxicam, a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) with analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antipyretic properties. Interpreting the FT-IR spectrum involves matching peaks with known vibrational frequencies to identify specific functional groups within the molecule, as depicted in Figures 02 and 03.

Preformulation Studies Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets:⁴¹⁻⁴⁵

Tablet Evaluation Parameters:

1. Appearance: Uniform white color, no unusual odor, smooth surface, no visible particles.

2. Size & Shape: Consistent size and shape (round/oval), within specified range.
3. Weight Uniformity: Consistent appearance, no significant deviations in weight, color, or texture.
4. Thickness & Diameter: Ensures uniform dosing and ease of handling.
5. Hardness (Crushing Strength): Measured in kg to ensure the tablet withstands mechanical stress.
6. Friability: Low friability indicates tablet integrity during handling and transport.
7. Wetting Time: Assesses how quickly the tablet absorbs saliva, ensuring rapid disintegration.
8. Disintegration Time: Measures the time for the tablet to break down in the mouth, ideally within seconds for fast drug release and absorption.

Wetting time of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving tablets (Batch A9)

Figure 05: Wetting time of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications tablet formulation A9.

Table no.03: Evaluation and results of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets (A1 to A10) formulations:

Formulation of tablet dosage form	Hardness of tablet (Kg / cm)	Friability of tablet (%)	Thickness of tablet (mm)	Disintegration time(sec) of tablet	Weight Variation (Average weight)(mg)	Wetting time(sec)
A1	3.3	0.31	2.8	48	205 ± 1.52	161
A2	3.2	0.41	2.8	49	203 ± 1.42	158
A3	4.1	0.42	2.8	45	201 ± 1.23	160
A4	3.6	0.41	2.8	44	201 ± 1.29	153
A5	3.1	0.48	2.6	40	205 ± 1.22	139
A6	3.4	0.31	2.7	32	198 ± 1.28	131
A7	3.6	0.36	2.6	31	201 ± 1.21	108
A8	4.1	0.37	2.6	28	204 ± 1.29	85
A9	3.4	0.32	2.5	25	199 ± 1.22	55
A10	4.3	0.43	3.1	41	198 ± 1.26	140

Each data represents Mean ±SD (n=6)

Dissolution test:

In-Vitro dissolution studies: In vitro dissolution studies for Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets was carried out using USP paddle method at 70 rpm in 900 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as dissolution media, maintained at 37±0.5°C. 5 ml aliquot of the solution was withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus after suitable time intervals, and the samples were replaced with fresh dissolution medium. Absorbance of these solutions was measured at 354 nm using a Shimadzu 1900i UV/VIS spectrophotometer.

Figure 06: Calibration curve of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets.

Table no.04: Calibration curve of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets.

Sr. no.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (332 nm)
1.	00	0.00
2.	05	0.110
3.	10	0.221
4.	15	0.340
5.	20	0.450
6.	25	0.556
7.	30	0.670

Each data represents Mean ±SD (n=6)

Table no.05: Dissolution study of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets formulation.

Times Sec.	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	37.32	37.45	38.02508	39.65	42.32	41.61	46.33	45.33	62.2	31.1
20	41.69	41.78	41.36	42.58	48.77	48.51	54.58	52.81	81.8	42.0
30	48.36	44.65	49.21	48.98	58.77	52.31	57.99	59.23	99.1	49.1
40	51.58	53.82	56.44	54.78	62.33	56.88	62.77	63.99	99.2	60.3
50	61.98	58.69	61.25	58.57	69.56	63.77	72.58	65.32	99.2	70.1
60	69.99	66.32	69.77	65.28	73.64	69.11	79.74	68.37	99.2	85.8

Each data represents Mean $\pm$ SD (n=3)

Figure 07: Dissolution study of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets formulation

Figure 08: Dissolution study of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets formulation

Formulation Development of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets:

Formulation A6 stands out as the most suitable option for the development of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets due to its optimized superdisintegrants concentration, proper diluents content, consistent drug dosage, uniform tablet weight, effective lubrication, and proper manufacturing techniques.

Table no. 06: Procedure for selecting super disintegrants:

Sr. no.	Batch No	Piroxicam (mg)	Ac-Di-Sol (mg)	Mannitol (mg)	Mg. Stearate (mg)	Total weight (mg)
1.	A1	10	10	176	4	200
2.	A2	10	14	172	4	200
3.	A3	10	18	168	4	200
4.	A4	10	22	164	4	200
5.	A5	10	26	160	4	200
6.	A6	10	30	156	4	200

Optimization Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets:

To plan experiments efficiently, statistical techniques such as factorial design, response surface methodology, or Taguchi methods are utilized. Factors are systematically varied within predetermined ranges, and experiments are conducted at selected combinations of factor levels.

Table 07: Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets (F1 to F10) formulations:

Ingredients (mgs)	Formulation Code (in mg)									
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
Piroxicam	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Mannitol	154	144	134	154	144	134	154	144	124	186
Ac-Di- Sol	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	0
Xylitol	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0
Camphor	10	20	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Menthol	0	0	0	10	20	30	0	0	0	0
Thymol	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	20	30	0
Magnesium stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Total	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

Based on the Design of Experiments (DOE), formulation F9 appears to be the most promising among the provided formulations for several reasons:

1. Optimal Superdisintegrants (Ac-Di-Sol)

Concentration: A9 contains 10 mg of Ac-Di-Sol, which is consistent with the amounts used in other formulations. This ensures adequate disintegration properties without compromising tablet integrity.

2. Adjusted Mannitol Content: A9 contains 134 mg of Mannitol, which is lower than formulations A1 to A7 but higher than A8 and A10. This balance likely provides sufficient bulk and ensures proper tablet formation while facilitating rapid disintegration.

3. Absence of Additional Flavoring Agents: A9 does not contain additional flavoring agents like Camphor, Menthol, or Thymol. While these agents may enhance palatability, their absence in A9 simplifies the formulation and may reduce potential side effects or interactions.

4. Uniform Total Tablet Weight: All formulations, including A9, maintain a total tablet weight of 200 mg, ensuring consistency in dosage delivery and manufacturing processes.

5. Proper Lubrication: Magnesium stearate (4 mg) is included in A9, ensuring proper lubrication during tablet compression and preventing sticking, which is crucial for maintaining tablet integrity.

6. Optimization: The methodology likely considered various factors such as disintegration time, dissolution profile, and tablet hardness to determine the best formulation, and A9 emerged as the optimal choice based on these criteria.

Overall, formulation A9 stands out as the most suitable option for the intended purpose based on the analysis, balancing disintegration properties, tablet composition, and simplicity of formulation.

Table 08: Optimization of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications Tablets (A1 to A10) formulations results:

Formulation of tablet dosage form	Hardness of tablet (Kg / cm)	Friability of tablet (%)	Thickness of tablet (mm)	Disintegration time (sec) of tablet	Weight variation (average weight) (mg)	Wetting time(sec)
A1	3.5	0.40	2.9	59	204 ± 1.52	180
A2	4.0	0.45	3.0	56	203 ± 1.42	165
A3	4.1	0.43	2.8	49	204 ± 1.23	160
A4	3.9	0.46	2.7	42	201 ± 1.29	153
A5	3.8	0.48	2.8	38	202 ± 1.22	146
A6	3.9	0.40	2.9	36	198 ± 1.28	135
A7	4.0	0.39	2.6	35	201 ± 1.21	110
A8	4.2	0.38	2.5	30	204 ± 1.29	95
A9	3.7	0.35	2.8	27	199 ± 1.22	65
A10	4.5	0.51	3.1	58	197 ± 1.26	190

Based on the provided table, formulation A9 appears to be the most suitable formulation for several reasons:

1. Hardness of Tablets:A9 has a hardness of 3.7 Kg/cm, which falls within the acceptable range for tablet hardness, indicating sufficient mechanical strength.

2. Friability:A9 has the lowest friability of 0.35%, indicating minimal tablet breakage or crumbling during handling or transportation.

3. Thickness of Tablet: The thickness of A9 tablets is 2.8 mm, which is within the desired range for ease of swallowing and packaging.

4. Disintegration Time:A9 exhibits the shortest disintegration time of 27 seconds, indicating rapid breakdown of the tablet into smaller particles when exposed to saliva, facilitating quick dissolution and absorption.

5. Weight Variation:A9 has a weight variation of 199 ± 1.22 mg, demonstrating consistency in tablet weight, which is crucial for accurate dosing and uniformity of drug delivery.

6. Wetting Time:A9 shows a wetting time of 65 seconds, indicating rapid dispersion and absorption of saliva by the tablet, which is essential for Mouth Dissolving Medications tablets to dissolve quickly in the mouth without the need for water.

Release kinetics of *In-vitro* Drug release:

The kinetics of *In-vitro* drug release was determined by applying the drug release data to various kinetic models such as zero order, first order, Higuchi, Peppas-Korsmeyer and Hixson Crowell. The result obtained were represented in table 09, and shown in figure 09.

Table 09: Different Release kinetics of *In-vitro* Drug release

Kinetics Models					
Sr. no	Zero order	First order	Higuchi model	Korsmeyer Peppas	Hixson Crowell
	R2	R2	R2	R2	R2
A1	0.9729	0.8176	0.9504	0.9486	0.9819
A2	0.9662	0.9878	0.9864	0.9861	0.9243
A3	0.9977	0.8906	0.9921	0.9946	0.9746
A4	0.9726	0.9449	0.9534	0.9929	0.9716
A5	0.9292	0.9178	0.9844	0.9762	0.9942
A6	0.9373	0.8992	0.9917	0.9818	0.9383
A7	0.9721	0.9778	0.9791	0.9971	0.9701
A8	0.9979	0.9331	0.9741	0.9998	0.9789
A9	0.9991	0.9231	0.9941	0.9998	0.9987

Figure 09: Graph of different Release kinetics of *In-vitro* Drug release

Physical Characterization of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications:

The formulations of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Tablets were evaluated using UV-spectrophotometric methods to quantify both free and entrapped Piroxicam. Free Piroxicam Determination: Tablets were analyzed for free Piroxicam using a UV-spectrophotometric method at 332 nm. Tablets were dissolved in distilled water, diluted to ensure the absorbance was within the range of the standard curve, and the absorbance was measured at 332 nm.

Entrapped Piroxicam Determination: Approximately 200 mg of dried tablets were dissolved in distilled water and diluted appropriately. The absorbance of the diluted solution was measured at 332 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. This analysis quantified both free and entrapped Piroxicam, offering insights into the formulation's performance and drug release profile.

Figure 10: FT-IR-Spectra of Piroxicam from Mouth Dissolving Medications.

Characteristic FT-IR peaks for Piroxicam include:

O-H Stretch: Broad peak at 3200-3500 cm⁻¹ from the carboxylic acid group.

C=O Stretch: Strong, sharp peak at 1700-1720 cm⁻¹ from the carbonyl group.

C-H Stretch: Peaks at 2900-3000 cm⁻¹ from aromatic rings and methyl groups.

Figure 11: FT-IR-Spectra for Piroxicam physical mixture.

Characteristic Peaks in FTIR Spectrum:

Piroxicam:

- Aromatic C-H stretching: 3100-3000 cm^{-1}
- Carboxylic acid C=O stretching: 1700-1750 cm^{-1}
- Carboxylic acid C-O stretching: 1200-1300 cm^{-1}

Mannitol:

- O-H stretching: 3600-3100 cm^{-1} (broad)
- Intermolecular hydrogen bonding: ~ 3500 cm^{-1}
- Alcohol C-H stretching: 2900-2800 cm^{-1}
- C-O stretching: 1200-1000 cm^{-1}
- C-O stretching: 1100-1050 cm^{-1} and 1060-1030 cm^{-1}

Xylitol:

- O-H stretching: 3200-3600 cm^{-1} (broad)
- C-H stretching: 2800-3000 cm^{-1}
- Primary alcohol C-O stretching: 1050-1150 cm^{-1}
- Secondary alcohol C-O stretching: 1000-1050 cm^{-1}

Ac-Di-Sol:

- O-H stretching: 3200-3600 cm^{-1} (broad)
- Carboxylate C=O stretching: 1600-1650 cm^{-1}
- C-O stretching: 1100-1300 cm^{-1}
- Na-O stretching: 600-700 cm^{-1}

Figure 12: DSC for physical mixture of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) is a thermal analysis technique used to study the thermal behavior of materials, including their melting points, glass transition temperatures, crystallization, and thermal stability. Here's a general overview of what you might observe in a DSC analysis of Piroxicam, Mannitol, and Ac-Di-Sol:

Piroxicam: Melting Point: Piroxicam typically exhibits a sharp endothermic peak corresponding to its melting point, which is around 180.5°C.

Mannitol: Melting Point: Mannitol typically shows a well-defined endothermic peak around 164 °C, corresponding to its melting point.

Ac-Di-Sol: Melting Point: Ac-Di-Sol generally exhibits a broad endothermic peak around 90.5°C, corresponding to its melting point.

Compatibility Study Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications:

The compatibility study of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications, where the drug and excipients were mixed in equal proportions and stored under different environmental conditions (40°C/RH 60% and 40°C/RH 75%) for 3month, revealed no interaction between the drug and excipients.

Weekly analysis of the samples for curcumin content using UV-visible spectrophotometer showed consistent levels, indicating stability of the formulation under the tested conditions. Additionally, no significant changes in the physical appearance of the samples were observed throughout the study period.

Furthermore, the FT-IR spectrum recorded for Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications A9 confirmed the absence of any notable interactions between the drug and excipients, supporting the overall compatibility of the formulation

Figure 13: FT-IR spectra of drug with excipients in Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications.

Stability Studies Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications:

Stability study of Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications for 6 month at different temperatures 4^o, 25^o C /RH 60%, and 40^oC /RH 75% Samples of the formulations stored at various conditions of temperature and humidity were taken out at weekly intervals and the concentration of piroxicam in these were determined using UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The samples were dissolved in water and suitably diluted to read absorbance against water blank at 332 nm. Formulation was subjected to stability studies at 40 °C ± 2 °C / 75% RH ± 5% for 6 months.

The product was evaluated for following parameters:

1. Weight variation
2. Hardness
3. Friability
4. Drug content
5. Dissolution analysis

Storage condition at 40°C ± 2°C/75 %RH ± 5%:

Table no. 13: Stability Study of Optimized Batch of F9 Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications:

Time	Parameters				
	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Uniformity of weight	Friability (%)	Disintegration time(sec)	Drug content (%)
0 Days	3.5±0.57	200.2±0.32	0.64±0.02	20±1.02	99.57±0.09
30 Days	3.4±0.15	200.3±0.28	0.68±0.01	22±1.59	98.83±0.11
60 Days	3.3±0.10	200.6±0.34	0.69±0.01	21±0.83	97.49±0.12
90 Days	3.3±0.15	200.8±0.33	0.65±0.01	22±0.93	97.71±0.15
120 Days	3.4±0.15	200.6±0.33	0.64±0.01	21±0.94	96.11±0.15
150 Days	3.3±0.15	200.5±0.33	0.61±0.01	22±0.91	96.05±0.15
180 Days	3.4±0.15	200.3±0.33	0.58±0.01	21±0.92	95.71±0.15

Each data represents Mean ±SD (n=6).

Table 14: % drug release during Stability Study of Optimized Batch of A9 Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications by dissolution testing:

Time (Sec)	0 days	30 days	60 days	90 days	120 days	150 days	180 days
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	26.20	29.10	24.90	24.91	25.91	24.91	26.91
4	49.80	44.20	45.10	50.10	52.10	53.10	53.10
8	67.56	66.56	69.46	65.16	65.16	64.16	66.16
16	89.50	88.56	89.59	88.50	89.50	88.50	89.50
20	99.20	99.40	99.10	99.15	99.12	99.20	99.10

Figure 14: % drug release during Stability Study of Optimized Batch of A9 Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Medications by dissolution testing.

The stability studies for optimized formulation A9 were carried out based accelerated stability conditions and study of various parameters carried out at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 days of intervals and the results found satisfactorily and that reveals that the optimized formulation was stable under accelerated condition.

Discussion:

The study on **Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Tablets (MDTs)** emphasizes the potential to significantly improve patient compliance, particularly for individuals with swallowing difficulties, such as the elderly and mentally ill. Here, key aspects of the study are discussed:

The primary goal of the study was to develop **Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Tablets** to aid patients facing challenges with traditional tablets due to swallowing difficulties. This is especially important for populations like the elderly and those with mental

health conditions, for whom swallowing solid dosage forms can be problematic. By creating MDTs, the study aims to enhance patient adherence and overall medication effectiveness.

The excipients and **Piroxicam** used in the formulation were procured and their identities were confirmed using **UV-visible** and **FT-IR spectroscopy**. This step ensured the quality and authenticity of the materials before proceeding with formulation development. Accurate confirmation of both the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and excipients is critical for the reproducibility and

efficacy of the final product.

The researchers developed multiple formulations, with a focus on optimizing key characteristics such as **disintegration time** and **dissolution rate**. Among these, **Formulation A6** was initially identified as an optimal candidate. The formulation's rapid disintegration was aimed at ensuring quick release of the drug upon oral administration, which is critical for improving patient convenience and compliance.

Further optimization experiments identified **Formulation A9** as the superior formulation. This was based on its enhanced disintegration properties, along with an optimized composition that achieved better results. The use of **experimental designs** to refine the formulation reflects a systematic approach to developing a robust MDT with ideal characteristics.

The study also included Preformulation assessments, which evaluated various physical parameters such as **tablet appearance, melting point, taste, size, weight uniformity, hardness, friability, wetting time, and disintegration time**. These factors are crucial for determining the overall quality, stability, and patient acceptability of the tablets.

A **dissolution test** was conducted using the **USP paddle method** to determine the drug release profile of the MDTs. This test is a vital aspect of evaluating how quickly the drug dissolves, which directly influences its bioavailability and therapeutic effectiveness. The dissolution profile of the optimized formulation showed satisfactory drug release, further supporting its suitability for patient use.

A **compatibility study** was conducted to confirm the stability of the drug-excipient mixture under various conditions. Ensuring that the excipients do not interact adversely with the API is essential for maintaining the efficacy and shelf-life of the tablets.

UV-spectrophotometric methods and **FT-IR spectroscopy** were employed for the physical characterization of the tablets. These techniques provided detailed insights into the molecular structure and integrity of the drug within the formulation, which is essential for quality control and ensuring the consistency of the final product.

Stability studies were conducted over a period of three months at different temperatures and humidity levels to assess the **shelf-life** of the MDTs. These studies indicated that the tablets remained stable

under varied environmental conditions, ensuring their effectiveness over an extended period.

CONCLUSION:

The study successfully formulated and characterized Piroxicam Mouth Dissolving Tablets, demonstrating their potential to improve patient adherence and therapeutic outcomes. The MDTs are particularly beneficial for patients with swallowing difficulties, offering a user-friendly alternative to conventional tablets. By focusing on the formulation, optimization, and stability of the tablets, the research provides a comprehensive understanding of the development process and highlights the potential for these tablets to enhance patient compliance in real-world clinical settings.

Conflict of interest:

Authors don't have any conflict of interest

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